

Energy Conversion Through Electrochemical Solar Cell Based on CdS Film Photoanode

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Electrochemical solar cells of the type CdS film/Polysulfide electrolyte/Pt, were prepared with n-CdS film deposited onto a (a) cadmium sheet and (b) titanium substrate. Under polychromatic excitation the cell characteristics were investigated. The onset of photoresponse was ~ 500 m μ , maximum conversion efficiency 0.13%, open circuit photopotential (V_{OC}) 0.62 volt, short circuit current (I_{SC}) 0.58 mA

and fill factor 0.36. It has been shown that it is possible to construct a regenerative photocell capable of acting as a sustained energy converter device. The poor cell efficiency has been attributed to lattice imperfections in the film.

SINCE the recent upsurge of interest in alternative energy sources many reports on electrochemical solar cells have appeared in the literature^{1,2}. But most of the investigations employed single crystal electrodes, since the bulk properties of the semiconductor can be controlled and their influence on cell performance can be more readily assessed. But for a solar cell to be suitable for terrestrial applications, attempts should be directed towards cheaper components and reduced fabrication costs. Consequently, polycrystalline materials are likely to replace single crystal photoelectrodes. With this end in view, the present communication deals with the preparation of photosensitive CdS electrode *in situ* by anodisation of (a) a cadmium sheet and (b) cadmium electrodeposited on a titanium substrate. With the photoelectrode thus prepared, cells of the type CdS/polysulfide electrolyte/Pt, were constructed and their performance under polychromatic excitation was investigated.

Experimental

Reagents :

Cadmium sheet used was of 99.999% purity, barium chloranilate, $C_6BaCl_2O_4 \cdot 3H_2O$ of E. Merck (Germany) grade and cadmium acetate, $(CH_3COO)_2Cd \cdot 2H_2O$, Sodium sulfide, $Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O$ of A. R. grade.

Electrodeposition of Cadmium upon Titanium Substrate :

Bright and smooth cadmium deposit of thickness $5-10 \times 10^{-6}$ m on titanium sheet was formed by the electrolysis of 0.4 moles/l cadmium acetate, 0.5 gm/l gelatin and 1.3 to 2.0 moles/l ethylene diamine maintaining the pH within 9-11 at temperature range 25-50° with a current density of 10-20 mA/cm² using platinum anode.

Preparation of CdS film :

CdS film was prepared by anodisation using either pure cadmium sheet or cadmium electrodeposited on a titanium sheet as anode and platinum cathode in a solution containing ~ 1.0 M Na_2S at pH 9-12, in an inert atmosphere at a constant current density of 2 mA/cm². The film so grown was dark yellow in color.

Construction of the photoelectrochemical cell (PEC) :

With CdS electrode so prepared the following cell was constructed :

in a glass vessel of 3.5 cm in diameter and 10 cm long.

Cathode : A pure platinum wire 9 cm long and 1 mm diameter, attached to a piece of platinum foil of area 4 cm².

Anode : CdS film formed either on the pure Cd sheet or Cd electrodeposited on titanium substrate was dried at 100° for one hour in nitrogen atmosphere and then etched in 1 M HCl at 60°. Ohmic contact with titanium sheet with a copper wire was made through indium and all the exposed metal insulated with epoxy resin.

Electrolyte : Polysulfide electrolyte was prepared by addition of 0.1 mol each of NaOH and $Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O$ and sublimed sulfur to 100 ml nitrogen purged distilled water.

Current-Voltage properties :

The V-I characteristics of the PEC so constructed were studied. The measurements were carried out

using a 1000 W tungsten lamp as the light source. Light intensity was measured by calibrating the lamp with a standard silicon solar cell. All measurements were carried out with polychromatic light, under constant nitrogen purge.

Wavelength response :

Relative photopotential as a function of excitation wavelength was determined by using Karl Zeiss filters in the front of the light emerged from 1000W tungsten lamp. The intensity of the emergent light from the filter was kept constant for all the wavelengths.

Thickness :

CdS layer from the substrate was scraped mechanically and quantitatively oxidised to sulfate by bromine in carbon tetrachloride solution, followed by nitric acid and the sulfate solution thus obtained was passed through Zeo Karb 225 ion exchange resin column. From the effluent obtained the sulfate was estimated using barium chloranilate reagent³ spectrophotometrically at 530 m μ . The thickness of the CdS layer was then computed assuming the surface as flat and the stoichiometry as CdS.

All results described hereafter refer to CdS film on titanium substrate unless otherwise specified.

Results and Discussion

Stability :

n-Type semiconductors are very prone to photoanodic dissolution. Stability of the photoanode is,

Fig. 1. Photocurrent as a function of time in cells containing 1 M NaOH (O) and 1 M NaOH, 1M Na₂S and 1 M S (●).

therefore, an essential requirement for a suitable energy converter device. By adding S₈²⁻ to the electrolyte, photoanodic dissolution can be quenched as has been shown in Fig. 1. In 1.0 M NaOH as the electrolyte the photocurrent falls rapidly. But by adding Na₂S and S, one molar each, to the same NaOH, 1.0 M, a very stable photocurrent was obtained. The short circuit current decreased only by 0.07 mA/cm², e.g., from 0.54 mA/cm² to 0.47 mA/cm² over a period of eight hours, whereas in 1.0 M NaOH as the electrolyte, the short circuit current decreased from 0.50 mA/cm² to 0.02 mA/cm² over a period of only eight minutes. With etched CdS as photoanode, larger photocurrent is obtained, but stability decreases. This probably arises from subtle changes in the surface states of the semiconductor film on etching.

Open circuit photopotential :

Open circuit photopotential was measured as a function of light intensity and the results are shown in Fig. 2. As is evident from the graph, the photopotential increases with light intensity and at sufficiently high intensity the photopotential tends to

Fig. 2. Photopotential against light intensity (●) and against logarithm of light intensity (O) for cell with 1 M NaOH, 1M Na₂S and 1 M S electrolyte.

exhibit a saturation effect. Furthermore in accordance with theory⁴, the photopotential varies linearly with the log of light intensity.

Wavelength response :

Relative photopotential as a function of excitation wavelength at a constant light intensity is

shown in Fig. 3. The electrolyte used was 1.0 M NaOH, 1.0 M Na₂S and 1.0 M S. For wavelengths

Fig. 3. Wavelength response curve for cell with 1.0 M NaOH, 1 M Na₂S and 1 M S electrolyte.

shorter than band gap response was observed, whereas excitations at higher wavelengths were ineffective, as expected.

Current-Voltage properties

Fig. 4 compares the current-voltage properties of n-CdS films formed on pure Cd sheet and on

Fig. 4. Current-voltage curves at 100 mw/cm² for cells based on CdS film on cadmium sheet, thickness 0.952×10^{-6} m (O), and CdS film on titanium sheet, thickness 0.905×10^{-6} m (●).

thin Cd plate on the titanium substrate from ethylene diamine bath. The open circuit photopotential was found to be approximately same but short circuit photocurrent slightly differs. The fill factors of both the curves are comparable, being of the value of ~ 0.36 . This compares favourably with an earlier value⁵ of 0.4 using a sprayed CdS film photoanode. The comparative values of the cell characteristics based on CdS films deposited onto (a) cadmium sheet and (b) titanium substrate are shown in Table 1.

Dependence of current-voltage properties on intensity and electrolyte composition was studied. Current-voltage curves (Fig. 5) were measured at

Fig. 5. Dependence of current voltage properties on intensity and electrolyte composition.

intensities 70 mw/cm² and 25 mw/cm² for n-CdS for 1.0 M NaOH, 1.0 M Na₂S electrolytes having

TABLE-1*

CELL CHARACTERISTICS WITH THE DIFFERENT PHOTOANODES PREPARED

CdS film on	t m	V _{OC} volts	I _{SC} mA	Fill Factor	η %
Cd sheet	0.952 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.62	0.58	0.36	0.13
Ti substrate	0.905 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.60	0.51	0.36	0.11

* Abbreviations : t—thickness ; V_{OC} —open circuit photopotential ; I_{SC} —short circuit current ;
η—maximum energy conversion efficiency.

variable amounts of sulfur. The sulfur concentration was varied from 0.1 M to 1 M. In all cases the low intensity curves were found to be very comparable. At high light intensity, with the decrease in total sulfur concentration the short circuit current decreases, but the open circuit photopotential does not change appreciably. The fill factors of the curves obtained at low intensities were found to be approximately same, whereas at high intensities as sulfur concentration is lowered, fill factor appreciably decreases. So, to obtain optimal current-voltage properties the composition of polysulfide electrolyte is crucial.

From the cell characteristics described above, it may be concluded that solar cells with polycrystalline CdS film as photoanode irradiated by composite light are less efficient than those with CdS single crystals⁶⁻⁸ and CdS film^{9,10} illuminated by monochromatic excitation. In a smuch as excitation wavelengths above the band gap of the semiconductor are inoperative, cells illuminated by composite light are expected to yield poor results. The main reason, however, lies in electron-hole recombination. By choosing a suitable redox system e.g., S²⁻/S₈²⁻ as in the present case, direct recombination at the photoelectrode surface may be minimised, but there may be a lot of recombination centres due to the lattice imperfections in the CdS film, and presence of impurities in the film. Nonetheless, it is possible to construct an electrochemical

solar cell, with CdS film as the photoanode, to act as a sustained energy converter device.

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